

TRANSNATURE

Policy Recommendations: Scheldt Estuary

Governance

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List of abbreviations

BD	Birds Directive
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
ESPOO	Convention on Environmental Impact Assessment in a Transboundary Context
HD	Habitats Directive
ISC	International Scheldt Commission
NbS	Nature based Solutions
NRL	Nature Restoration Regulation
SAC	Special Area of Conservation (under the Habitats Directive)
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
VNSC	Flemish-Dutch Scheldt Commission
WFD	Water Framework Directive

Introduction

Transboundary cooperation in the field of biodiversity protection is a relatively understudied governance mechanism in Europe. The project “[TRANSNATURE](#) – TRANSboundary governance models of biodiversity protection: case studies for an enhanced protection of NATURAL resources in Europe” aims to fill this gap by focusing on four case studies, including the Scheldt Estuary, covering Flanders (Belgium) and the Netherlands.

After fieldwork carried out between April and December 2024 (23 interviews and one focus group), policy recommendations have been formulated to suggest avenues to improve the current mechanisms of cross-border cooperation in the Scheldt estuary, and ultimately to strengthen biodiversity conservation and sustainable development in the case study area.

The recommendations presented draw mainly from the inputs on challenges and visions collected during the fieldwork, complemented by evidence in literature and case law. The main categories of stakeholders involved are authorities (national, regional and local), research institutes, agricultural organizations, environmental organizations, citizens initiatives and port-related organizations. All recommendations developed in the four TRANSNATURE case studies are developed around the elements of “coordination”, “participation” and “funding”. For the Scheldt Case, the category of integration has been added, based on stakeholder feedback to this document. In the case of the Scheldt Estuary, the focus is on the alignment of biodiversity targets, the degree of citizen participation, the degree of integration of biodiversity protection and climate adaptation, as well as the availability funding for smaller citizen initiatives as well as more large-scale restoration efforts.

This document was initially developed as a draft for the stakeholders and participants involved in the TRANSNATURE project. It was presented and discussed with stakeholders in October

2025, and the feedback and comments received during this process were used to revise and refine the policy recommendations. The current version reflects these stakeholder evaluations regarding the importance of the recommendations for cooperation, as well as their feasibility and relevance to local needs and priorities.

It is important to note that the document starts with existing baselines, e.g restoration targets and conservation objectives, as well as forms of transboundary coordination, such as the bilateral Scheldt treaties, the 'Ontwikkelingsschets 2010' and the VNSC procedures. At the same time, the recommendations explicitly respond to emerging EU-level legal developments, in particular the recently adopted Nature Restoration Law (NRL). While restoration and conservation obligations remain largely organised at the national level, the NRL introduces binding restoration requirements that create a new sense of urgency and provide a legal and policy 'hook' for organising ecosystem restoration at the scale of the estuary, transcending national borders. The recommendations therefore also seek to connect existing transboundary governance arrangements with these new restoration obligations.

PART I: Coordination

Policy Recommendation 1

Balance biodiversity and restoration framework for the Scheldt Estuary using the EU Nature Restoration Regulation to translate knowledge into coordinated, time-bound action

Summary:

Biodiversity restoration in the Scheldt Estuary is not constrained by a lack of joint knowledge (development). Extensive joint fact-finding and baseline studies, including the *Langetermijnperspectief Natuur* and *Systeem Analyse*, have already established a shared understanding of habitat status, species populations, ecological priorities, and conservation objectives on both sides of the border. The main challenge lies in translating this knowledge into concrete, coordinated, and time-bound restoration measures. This recommendation proposes establishing a joint biodiversity and restoration framework that aligns existing Natura 2000 obligations, including Birds and Habitats Directive objectives for estuarine habitats and species, with the EU Nature Restoration Regulation (NRL). Using the NRL's phased timelines (2030, 2040, 2050) as a structuring mechanism, the framework aims to overcome implementation standstills and ensure ecosystem-level recovery, rather than focusing solely on habitat-specific targets.

Context and problem:

The ecological priorities and current state of the Scheldt Estuary are well known, providing a strong foundation for action. Despite clearly defined conservation objectives, implementation measures differ between Flanders and the Netherlands. There is insufficient coordination on the sequencing, timing, and prioritization of restoration actions, which limits the ecological effectiveness of restoration and eventually risks non-compliance with the NRL. Current approaches often focus on habitat-specific targets rather than taking a phased, ecosystem-level perspective.

Without coordinated implementation, the NRL's 2030, 2040, and 2050 targets are not likely to be fully translated into effective restoration in the Scheldt area. The key challenge is not the targets themselves, but the lack of alignment in cross-border actions and measures: procedural delays and political standstills have left well-understood objectives unimplemented, and a coordinated framework is needed to ensure that existing obligations are translated into concrete, time-bound restoration actions, explicitly linked to the NRL to create a clear legal and operational imperative for implementation (the needed '*sense of urgency*').

Addressees:

Primary addressees are the Dutch and Flemish environmental authorities responsible for Natura 2000 management and the implementation of the EU Nature Restoration Regulation. Addressees can also include regional water and land management agencies involved in restoration planning and implementation.

Recommendation:

To address these challenges, the Dutch and Flemish authorities could establish a **joint biodiversity and restoration framework** for the Scheldt Estuary that:

- **Build on existing baselines**

The framework could leverage the extensive joint studies and analyses, including the Langetermijnperspectief Natuur and the System Analysis, to provide a detailed understanding of habitat conditions, species populations, and conservation objectives on both sides of the border. It is important to emphasize that the key challenge is not a lack of knowledge or quantitative targets, but the alignment of cross-border actions, responsibilities, and timelines to ensure effective implementation.

- **Define phased ecosystem restoration targets**

Clear, stepwise restoration targets could be established for 2030, 2040, and 2050 - fully aligned with the NRL's deadlines. These targets should go beyond individual habitat or species objectives to focus on restoring healthy, resilient estuarine ecosystems. Both quantitative goals, such as habitat area and species populations, and qualitative indicators of ecosystem health, including habitat quality and functional connectivity, should be integrated to ensure comprehensive ecosystem recovery.

- **Align cross-border measures, prioritization, and timing**

A shared operational roadmap/plan (aligned with Art. 14(7) NRL) could coordinate which restoration measures are implemented where, in what sequence, and under whose responsibility. This plan/roadmap could include a coordinated monitoring and adaptive management system to track progress (building on existing monitoring and management mechanisms), ensure compliance with NRL obligations, and enable timely adjustments. By aligning Dutch and Flemish actions in this way, the framework creates a legal and practical sense of urgency to overcome procedural delays and political standstills, ensuring that well-understood objectives are translated into concrete, time-bound restoration measures.

By consolidating existing knowledge while establishing cross-border alignment and NRL compliance, this framework will ensure that restoration efforts in the Scheldt Estuary are ecologically coherent, actionable, and delivered within legally mandated timeframes.

Added value:

These recommendations aim to create a practical mechanism to turn well-established knowledge and conservation objectives into concrete, implemented restoration actions. It explicitly integrates the NRL's phased targets and ecosystem-level perspective, ensuring that restoration efforts are not limited to habitat-specific outcomes and that transboundary cooperation is strengthened. By linking existing baselines, Natura 2000 obligations, and the NRL's phased targets (2030, 2040, 2050) to time-bound measures, authorities can move towards further practical implementation - overcoming the current standstill in the Scheldt Estuary. By doing so, it provides a clear, actionable roadmap/plan to achieve long-term, climate-resilient ecosystem restoration.

Policy Recommendation 2

- **a: Establish a joint transboundary appropriate assessment procedure (under Article 6(3) Habitats Directive)**
- **b: Strengthen transboundary environmental consultation and advice mechanisms under the Espoo Convention and SEA Directive**

Summary:

Environmental permitting in the Scheldt Estuary is undermined by inconsistent and sometimes even conflicting pollution standards and procedures between Flanders and the Netherlands—particularly concerning substances like PFAS and nitrogen. This misalignment and lack of full harmonisation negatively impact effective ecological protection, creates legal uncertainty, and complicates the assessment of cumulative cross-border impacts. The recommendation is to establish a joint transboundary appropriate assessment procedure under Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive, supported by the (better implementation of) Espoo Convention, SEA, and EIA Directives, to ensure use of scientific baselines, ensure early consultation, and improve coordination in permitting decisions. This would enhance legal compliance, reduce delays, and protect the integrity of the estuary's Natura 2000 sites.

Context and problem:

The Scheldt Estuary is subject to overlapping environmental obligations under EU law (e.g. the Habitats Directive and WFD), but Flanders and the Netherlands apply different standards, thresholds, and procedures in pollution-related permitting, for example in the case of nitrogen and PFAS. These differences affect how environmental impacts are assessed, what levels of pollution are deemed acceptable, and how mitigation measures are evaluated. As a result, the ecological coherence and legal certainty of transboundary pollution are undermined, and cumulative impacts on shared ecosystems are insufficiently addressed.

Although legal instruments such as the Espoo Convention, the SEA Directive, and Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive provide a framework for transboundary consultation and assessment, these mechanisms are not systematically or consistently applied, including in the Scheldt Estuary context. While the VNSC supports joint scientific monitoring and modelling efforts, e.g. through programmes like MONEOS¹, which underpin shared understanding of hydrological, morphological, and ecological dynamics, there is currently no dedicated, jointly agreed scientific baseline or threshold framework for pollution-related permitting. Critical variables such as nitrogen deposition, PFAS concentrations, or cumulative pollutant impacts on Natura 2000 sites are assessed using different national (and/or regional) standards and assumptions, which complicates transboundary evaluations. Moreover, there is no joint procedural framework for how to apply these assessments under legal instruments, such as Habitats Directive.

¹ Scheldemonitor, available at: <https://www.scheldemonitor.be/nl/monitoringsprogramma-moneos>.

Cross-border use of existing EU tools (e.g. Espoo Convention, SEA Directive, Article 6(3) HD) remains rather ad hoc and case-driven, or based on public pressure, rather than embedded in a systematic and institutionalised transboundary permitting procedure.

The Transnature research (Scheldt Estuary case study) focused, amongst others, on the role of VNSC. In this context it is important that the VNSC, the main bilateral platform for policy and management of the Scheldt Estuary, does *not* have a formal mandate to address pollution-related permitting or the harmonisation of environmental standards. As a result, pollution-related impacts fall outside the VNSC's operational scope, and there is no dedicated institutional setting to deal with them at transboundary level.

The consequences of this fragmented approach are evident. Thresholds for PFAS substances in drinking water are currently defined at the national and/or regional level as advisory values, based on scientific risk assessments, but are not (yet) embedded in binding legislation or regulatory permitting frameworks. Flanders allows significantly higher thresholds for PFAS substances (e.g., TFA up to 15.6 µg/L)² than the Netherlands (2.2 µg/L)³, leading to divergent evaluations of risk and compliance.

Similarly, there are different approaches to nitrogen permitting: Flanders uses a threshold regime for nitrogen,⁴ while the Netherlands used to rely on the PAS system, which has been invalidated by the Dutch Council of State in 2019.^{5/6} The applicable thresholds vary significantly, with Flanders clearly opting for more flexible thresholds in the context of its permitting policy regarding nitrogen deposition on Natura 2000 areas.⁷ This results in uncertainty around cumulative impact assessment and acceptable deposition levels, especially in a transboundary context. Cases like the INEOS project⁸, a major economic project authorized by the Flemish authorities in the Port of Antwerp, illustrate how lack of coordination prolongs conflict and delays decision-making. In the previous years, the permits for this industrial facility have been repeatedly quashed by administrative courts, partially as a result of lawsuits launched by Dutch authorities. The main reason for this increase in transboundary litigation is the lack of harmonized approach to nitrogen pollution between the Netherlands and Flanders.

Ultimately, the absence of harmonised procedures and standards risks undermining compliance with EU law, particularly regarding achieving good ecological status of bodies of surface water (Annex V to the WFD) and non-deterioration of natural habitats (Art 6(2) Habitats Directive) as well as the requirement for an appropriate assessment under (Art. 6(3) Habitats Directive)⁹. Without a shared (cross-border) understanding of what constitutes 'significant impact',

² Vlaanderen.be (15. November 2014), available at: <https://www.vlaanderen.be/pfas-vervuiling/advieswaarde-tfa-in-drinkwater>.

³ RIVM.nl (7 April 2023), available at: <https://www.rivm.nl/documenten/bijlage-bij-rivm-brief-aan-ilt-indicatieve-drinkwaterrichtwaarde-trifluorazijnzuur-tfa#:~:text=De%20indicatieve%20drinkwaterrichtwaarde%20bedraagt%20200,worden%20gehouden%20in%20de%20risicobeoordeling>.

⁴ Vlaanderen.be (4 July 2025), available at: <https://www.vlaanderen.be/stikstof-in-vlaanderen/update-impactscoretool-impact-en-depositietrendtool>.

⁵ <https://www.rechtspraak.nl/Organisatie-en-contact/Organisatie/Raad-van-State/Nieuws/Paginas/PAS-mag-niet-als-toestemmingsbasis-voor-activiteiten-worden-gebruikt.aspx>.

⁶ RIVM (2024), available at: <https://www.rivm.nl/bibliotheek/rapporten/2024-0076.pdf>.

⁷ H. Schoukens, 'The ineos Case and the Transnational Dimension of the Habitats Directive: in Search of a Level Playing Field in Times of Transboundary Nitrogen Wars?', (2025) *Journal for European Environmental & Planning Law*, 22(1-2), 49-75. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18760104-22010203>.

⁸ Case of 20 July 2023, RvVb-A-2223-1097, available at: <https://www.dbrc.be/sites/default/files/2023-08/RVVB.A.2223.1097.pdf>.

⁹ As confirmed by CJEU rulings, such as the Weser case (C-461/13).

biodiversity protection, including that of the Scheldt Estuary, remains vulnerable to fragmented governance and suboptimal ecological outcomes.

Addressees:

- National environmental permitting authorities in Flanders (e.g. Departement Omgeving, VMM) and the Netherlands (Rijkswaterstaat)
- Competent authorities for Natura 2000 and WFD
- Cross-border EIA/SEA focal points and competent bodies

Recommendation:

To avoid further diplomatic conflicts and court room battles between Dutch and Flemish authorities more attention could go to the establishment of common standards and (procedural) guidelines for the appropriate assessment procedure under Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive, which might be particularly relevant for addressing transboundary nature of biodiversity impacts in the Scheldt Estuary. Such efforts could serve as a crucial first step toward harmonizing how pollution-related impacts, especially from PFAS and nitrogen, are evaluated across borders.

- **Key elements of an appropriate assessment**

An appropriate assessment under Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive requires a rigorous, scientific evaluation of whether a plan or project is likely to have a significant effect on the integrity of a Natura 2000 site, considering its conservation objectives. This assessment must be conducted before any authorization or consent is granted, ensuring that potential impacts are fully understood in advance (Art. 6(3), HD). The assessment under Article 6(3) (and (4)) involves first screening to identify potential significant effects on a Natura 2000 site, followed by a detailed appropriate assessment of those effects, and, if necessary, allowing projects to proceed only for overriding public interest with compensatory measures to protect the site's integrity (see ANNEX 1). According to the CJEU (e.g., Waddenzee),¹⁰ such an assessment must eliminate any reasonable scientific doubt about potential adverse effects on the integrity of a Natura 2000 site. Key elements of the appropriate assessment, based on Art. 6(3) Habitats Directive, and as further clarified by CJEU case law and the Commission's 2021 Guidance (C/2021/437/01)¹¹:

- Exclusion of mitigation measures at the screening stage: Before carrying out an appropriate assessment, authorities must determine whether the plan or project is likely to have a significant effect on a Natura 2000 site. This screening stage must exclude any mitigation measures — their relevance can only be considered later in the assessment phase¹².

¹⁰ Case C-127/02, para. 71.4, available at: <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?text=&docid=49452&pageIndex=0&doclang=en&mode=lst&dir=&occ=first&part=1&cid=11870357>.

¹¹ Commission Notice, C 437/01 (2021), Assessment of plans and projects in relation to Natura 2000 sites – Methodological guidance on the provisions of Article 6(3) and (4) of the Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC, available at: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52021XC1028\(02\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52021XC1028(02)).

¹² The People Over Wind Case (C-323/17), para 40 '[...] as meaning that, in order to determine whether it is necessary to carry out, subsequently, an appropriate assessment of the implications, for a site concerned, of a plan or project, it is not appropriate, at the screening stage, to take account of the measures intended to avoid or reduce the harmful effects of the plan or project on that site'. Available at: <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?sessionId=DF029E034B6D0E9F1472FFE38BC2286E?text=&docid=200970&pageIndex=0&doclang=en&mode=lst&dir=&occ=first&part=1&cid=11828599>. See also Section 3.1 of the 2021 Commission Notice.

- Rigorous and science-based assessment: the appropriate assessment must be based on the best scientific knowledge, consider all aspects of the plan or project, and evaluate whether site integrity might be affected¹³.
 - Assessment of cumulative effects: the appropriate assessment must evaluate in-combination effects with other existing, approved, or reasonably foreseeable plans or projects. This ensures that combined impacts do not undermine site integrity, even if individual impacts appear limited.¹⁴
 - Assessment in view of conservation objectives: the analysis must be conducted in light of the site's conservation objectives, i.e., the reasons for which the site was designated¹⁵.
 - Outcome must rule out adverse effect beyond reasonable doubt: the authorization can only be granted if the competent authority is certain that there will be no adverse effect on site integrity¹⁶.
- **Current gaps in the Scheldt estuary context**

In the Scheldt Estuary, which hosts interconnected Natura 2000 sites on both the Flemish and Dutch sides, the legal obligations of Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive are not yet fully operationalised in a transboundary manner. Although both Member States must assess the potential impacts of plans and projects on both Dutch as well as Flemish Natura 2000 sites, current practice lacks the necessary coordination to ensure legally compliant and ecologically coherent outcomes across borders. Gaps that (can) impact the appropriate assessment in the case of the Scheldt Estuary include:

- Lack of institutionalised mechanisms for conducting *joint* appropriate assessments. Currently, the Netherlands and Flanders carry out assessments independently, without a formalised process for jointly evaluating cross-border ecological effects. This separation is problematic given the shared nature of estuarine ecosystems and undermines the requirement for a comprehensive assessment that considers the full extent of impacts. Projects that are authorised in Flanders, are not necessarily recognized as 'legal' in the Dutch context and vice versa. The lack of common standards illustrates the many disparities in the permitting policies of Flanders and the Netherlands.
- Lack of coherence in applied scientific baselines or thresholds to define what constitutes a 'significant effect' on the Natura 2000 area. As discussed above (main problem), different national standards for pollutants, such as nitrogen and PFAS, result in inconsistencies in how environmental impacts are assessed during permitting procedures. Since appropriate assessments must be rigorous, science-based, and capable of ruling out adverse effects beyond reasonable scientific doubt,¹⁷ such inconsistencies undermine the integrity of the assessment process. In practice, this means that identical or similar projects may be evaluated differently across the border,

¹³ Waddenzee Case, (C-127/02), para 71.4, available at: <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?text=&docid=49452&pageIndex=0&doclang=en&mode=lst&dir=&occ=first&part=1&cid=11870357>. See also Section 3.2.5 of the 2021 Commission Notice.

¹⁴ Confirmed in Moorburg Case C-142/16, para's 56-63, available at: <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?text=&docid=190143&pageIndex=0&doclang=en&mode=lst&dir=&occ=first&part=1&cid=12027022>. See also Section 3.1.4 of the 2021 Commission Notice.

¹⁵ Art. 6(3) Habitats Directive. See also Section 3.1.5 of the 2021 Commission Notice.

¹⁶ Waddenzee case C-127/02, para's. 57-59. See also Section 3.2.2 of the 2021 Commission Notice.

¹⁷ Waddenzee Case C-127/02, para's. 59 and 61.

leading to legal uncertainty, potential non-compliance with EU law, and inadequate protection of shared Natura 2000 sites.

- Cumulative impacts are not adequately assessed across borders. While effects should be considered ‘in combination with other plans or projects’, current procedures in the Scheldt estuary area do not systematically capture impact, such as combined nitrogen deposition or PFAS pollution from both sides of the border. Nonetheless, this is required by Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive.
- There is no *shared* procedural framework or timeline for conducting assessments, exchanging data, or reaching conclusions jointly. The absence of procedural alignment weakens legal certainty, creates risks of contradictory decisions, and hinders timely conflict resolution, as is illustrated by the recent court cases.

These gaps limit the effectiveness of Article 6(3) in protecting the Scheldt estuary’s Natura 2000 network and highlight the urgent need for a coordinated, transboundary approach to appropriate assessments. Common standards and (procedural) guidelines could lead to a further alignment of the permitting procedures and the appropriate assessments in light of Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive.

- **Bridging the gap:**¹⁸**integrating the ESPOO Convention and EIA/SEA Directives into a joint appropriate assessment for the Habitats Directive.**

2021 Commission Notice

5.2.1. *Opportunities for and benefits of streamlining EIA/SEA and appropriate assessment* Transboundary impacts:

Article 7 of the EIA Directive sets the provisions for assessing projects with transboundary impacts, including the requirements to inform another Member State where likely significant effects of a plan or project are envisaged on that Member State. The Member State that may be affected can then participate in the assessment if it so wishes. The EU has signed the Convention on Environmental Impact Assessment in a Transboundary Context (the Espoo Convention). In order to coordinate and facilitate the assessment procedures for cross-border projects, and in particular to conduct consultations in accordance with the Convention, the Member States concerned may set up a joint body, on the basis of equal representation.

Transboundary consultations are also envisaged and regulated under the SEA Directive (Article 7). These provisions on transboundary consultations are also highly relevant in terms of the overall goals of the Birds and Habitats Directives and the Natura 2000 network. This is because they provide an important preventive tool during the appropriate assessment of a plan or project whose adverse effects could jeopardise these goals in a neighbouring Member State.

See ANNEX 2 for ‘Comparison of procedures under appropriate assessment (AA), EIA and SEA’.

To facilitate a *joint* application of Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive in the Scheldt Estuary, particularly in light of differing standards for pollutants such as nitrogen and PFAS, existing EU legal instruments provide important procedural avenues for strengthening cross-border assessment. In particular, the ESPOO Convention¹⁹, the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)

¹⁸ See: Balias, G. (2019). The Appropriate Assessment under the European Habitats Directive: Interplay Between Science, Law, and Policy: in *Journal of International Wildlife Law and Policy*, Volume 21, 2018, available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13880292.2018.1551477>.

¹⁹ Convention on Environmental Impact Assessment in a Transboundary Context. Espoo, Finland, 25 February 1991, available at: https://treaties.un.org/doc/Treaties/1991/02/19910225%2008-29%20PM/Ch_XXVII_04p.pdf.

Directive²⁰ and the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive²¹ offer complementary frameworks that can be used to support the development of a joint, transboundary appropriate assessment. While the Habitats Directive imposes a substantive obligation to ensure that plans or projects do not adversely affect the integrity of Natura 2000 sites, the EIA and SEA Directives establish procedural obligations to assess environmental impacts — including across borders — and to ensure early public participation and intergovernmental consultation.

These procedural duties are based on the obligations of the Espoo Convention (1991), which requires Parties to notify and consult each other on activities likely to cause significant adverse transboundary environmental impacts. Under the EIA Directive,²² Member States must engage in transboundary consultation when a project is likely to have significant environmental effects in another Member State. The SEA Directive contains a parallel provision on transboundary consultations for plans and programmes²³. Together, these instruments create a multi-layered legal framework that supports the integration of transboundary environmental considerations into national decision-making processes. In the context of the Scheldt estuary, this integrated framework allows Flanders and the Netherlands to align their assessments under Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive with the procedural safeguards of the EIA and SEA Directives, as well as the obligations under the Espoo Convention.

These procedural requirements can directly support a joint appropriate assessment under Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive in several ways:

- Triggering transboundary coordination: The Habitats Directive (Article 6(3)) does not explicitly require transboundary consultation, even when a plan or project may affect Natura 2000 sites across national borders. However, applying the rationale of the transboundary nature of the Natura 2000 Network, it would be inconsistent not to include impacts on such protected sites that originate from foreign activities. Also, the Espoo Convention (Articles 2(4) and 3) and both the EIA Directive (Article 7(1)) and SEA Directive (Article 7(1)) establish a clear obligation to notify and consult affected states when significant environmental impacts are likely to cross borders, providing the ‘legal trigger’ for initiating cross-border cooperation.
- Ensure public participation across borders: Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive contains no explicit requirement for public participation, including in neighbouring countries potentially affected by a project. However, this provision is to be read in light of the Espoo Convention (Article 2(2) and (6) and 3(8))²⁴, the EIA Directive (Articles 6 and 7)²⁵, and SEA Directive (Articles 6 and 7)²⁶ which require that the public in both the originating and affected states be consulted during environmental assessments, ensuring early and inclusive stakeholder engagement/public participation.

²⁰ Directive 2011/92/EU as amended by 2014/52/EU, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02011L0092-20140515>.

²¹ Directive (2001/42/EC, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32001L0042>

²² Article 7(1) EIA Directive.

²³ Article 7 SEA Directive.

²⁴ Art. 1(x) ESPOO defines ‘the public’ as ‘one or more natural or legal persons’.

²⁵ Art. 1 (d) defines ‘public’ as one or more natural or legal persons and, in accordance with national legislation or practice, their associations, organisations or groups; Article 1(e) defines ‘public concerned’ as the public affected or likely to be affected by, or having an interest in, the environmental decision-making procedures referred to in Article 2(2). For the purposes of this definition, non-governmental organisations promoting environmental protection and meeting any requirements under national law shall be deemed to have an interest.

²⁶ Art. 2(d) defines ‘the public’ as one or more natural or legal persons and, in accordance with national legislation or practice, their associations, organisations or groups.

- Facilitating transboundary data exchange: While Article 6(3) Habitats Directive requires that appropriate assessments be based on the ‘best scientific knowledge in the field’,²⁷ it does not establish procedures for cross-border data exchange or collaboration. This is addressed by the Espoo Convention (Articles 3 and 4), the EIA Directive (Article 7(2)), and the SEA Directive (Article 7(2)), which require that environmental documentation is shared with the (likely) affected states and that they be given the opportunity to participate in the assessment process. These obligations could facilitate the mutual exchange of scientific information, such as pollution thresholds, deposition models, and ecological data, supporting the development of a joint scientific baseline (currently organised by the VNSC for the Scheldt area).
- Enabling coordinated assessment covering transboundary cumulative impacts: The Habitats Directive’s (Art. 6(3)) establishes a substantive obligation to assess plans and projects both individually and ‘in combination with other plans or projects’ but, as mentioned above, lacks procedural mechanisms for such transboundary assessments. The EIA Directive (Art. 7(1) and SEA Directive (Art. 7(1)) require consultation with affected Member States when transboundary impacts may occur, and mandate assessment of significant effects, including cumulative impacts from interactions with other plans or projects (EIA Directive Art. 5(1) and Annex IV,²⁸ and SEA Directive Art. 5(1) and Annex I²⁹).

Complementing these, the Espoo Convention provides a framework for notification, consultation, and exchange of environmental information on projects likely to cause significant transboundary impacts (Espoo Convention, Art. 3–5). These instruments support the procedural coordination necessary to assess cumulative effects on shared cross-border ecosystems, such as the Scheldt Estuary, thereby giving practical effect to Article 6(3) HD’s requirement to assess plans and projects ‘in combination’.

- Indication of procedural steps and timelines: The Habitats Directive does not offer a procedural roadmap or timelines for conducting an appropriate assessment under Article 6(3). Guidance can be found in the Espoo Convention (Art. 3(2)), requiring the indication of a reasonable timeframe for public consultation, and the EIA Directive (Articles 5–8), and SEA Directive (Art. 5–8) providing procedural requirements, including on the content of reports, consultation timeframes, and integration into decision-making, supporting legal certainty and transparency.

Added value:

Management within the Scheldt Estuary, including cross-border environmental permit procedures, pollution control, and habitat protection, is hindered by a lack of harmonised standards and procedures, such as for pollutants like PFAS and nitrogen. This leads to fragmented assessments, legal uncertainty, and delayed and contested decision-making. Implementing joint appropriate assessments under Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive, supported by procedural guidance from the EIA and SEA Directives and the Espoo Convention, offers a practical solution to these challenges.

²⁷ Waddenzee Case C-127/02, para. 61 and 71(4).

²⁸ Annex IV (5) provides that: A description of the likely significant effects of the project on the environment resulting from, inter alia: (e) the cumulation of effects with other existing and/or approved projects, taking into account any existing environmental problems relating to areas of particular environmental importance likely to be affected or the use of natural resources.

²⁹ Annex I (1) states that ‘these effects should include secondary, cumulative, synergistic, short, medium and long-term permanent and temporary, positive and negative effects.’

A more coordinated approach enables more comprehensive, resilient, consistent assessments, reducing administrative burdens, the speeding up of permitting processes, and limiting legal uncertainty across borders. This could consist of the adoption of common standards and mutually agreed benchmarks, to be applied in the context of Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive. This might enhance ecological coherence by allowing Flanders and the Netherlands to jointly assess cumulative impacts on shared Natura 2000 sites based on scientific assessments. Moreover, it can reduce confusion and uncertainty caused by neighbouring countries affecting each other through different standards.

PART II: Participation

Policy Recommendation 3

Develop a pilot on a ‘living consultation’ mechanisms in the Scheldt Estuary

Summary:

Public participation in the Scheldt Estuary remains largely ‘procedural’ and ‘static’, failing to reflect the dynamic and cumulative nature of environmental pressures such as nitrogen, PFAS, and climate change. Court room cases, like INEOS, show that insufficient and non-adaptive consultation contributes to public distrust, litigation, and delays. While Espoo and Aarhus obligations require early and effective participation, these are not systematically applied, especially for transboundary impacts. To address this, Flanders and the Netherlands could pilot a ‘living consultation’ model, involving continuous and inclusive stakeholder engagement throughout the life cycle of major projects and restoration efforts. This approach would improve transparency, strengthen compliance with EU and international law, and enhance legitimacy in environmental governance.

Context and problem:

Recent court rulings indicate that while more attention is now paid to direct habitat loss in port expansion and other development plans, indirect and cumulative environmental stressors—such as atmospheric nitrogen deposition, persistent organic pollutants (POPs), and climate change—are still often overlooked in current permitting and planning policies.³⁰ In the Scheldt Estuary, recent litigation, such as the INEOS case, for example shows that climate-related arguments are increasingly central to legal proceedings challenging economic development. Such cases reveal that permitting decisions have, until recently, paid limited attention to the cumulative environmental burden from multiple stressors, particularly in the Port of Antwerp and surrounding areas.³¹

A key issue is that transboundary environmental impacts—and especially their cumulative dimensions—might not have been consistently addressed in the application of EIA procedures. While the Espoo Convention has been implemented in EU law via the EIA Directive, and

³⁰ Schoukens, H. and N. van der Burgt (upcoming book chapter 2026): Cross-border pollution in the context of the Scheldt estuary: the complex search for a sustainable level playing field?

³¹ Ibid.

notification procedures under Article 7 have been applied in major infrastructure projects in the Scheldt Estuary, recent case law highlights the need for a more widespread and systematic application of Espoo rules in permitting procedures with likely cross-border consequences³². For instance, not all PFAS-related permits issued by Flemish authorities were not communicated to the Dutch government, which remained unaware of their potential transboundary impacts.³³ This undermines the transparency and cooperative spirit required under Espoo and EU environmental law.

The Espoo Convention defines ‘impact’ in broad terms, including ‘any effect caused by a proposed activity on the environment including human health and safety, flora, fauna, soil, air, water, climate’.³⁴ In addition, the concept of ‘transboundary impact’ covers ‘any impact, not exclusively of a global nature, within an area under the jurisdiction of a Party caused by a proposed activity the physical origin of which is situated wholly or is part within the jurisdiction of another party’.³⁵ These definitions imply that projects involving hazardous pollutants, climate risk, or diffuse emissions—even when not large-scale infrastructure works—may fall within the Convention’s scope.

At the same time, public participation in the Scheldt Estuary remains largely procedural and ‘static’, typically confined to formal consultations at set stages, mostly in the context of permitting and planning procedures. This static and reactive approach does not reflect the complex, dynamic ecological reality of the estuary or the evolving regulatory context. As cumulative pressures and transboundary risks increase, citizen and civil society engagement must become more adaptive, inclusive, and ongoing—not only to improve decision-making but also to reduce legal risk and strengthen democratic legitimacy. This is underscored by obligations under the Aarhus Convention, which require timely, effective public participation (Art. 6–8).

Finally, the recent adoption of the Nature Restoration Law significantly clearly raises the bar for ecological assessment and action. It introduces binding EU-wide and national targets and mandates the development of National Restoration Plans, calling on Member States to foster cooperation where ecosystems span borders (Art. 14(7) NRL), reinforcing the need for transboundary coordination and transparency in restoration-related decision-making.

In short, public consultation and participation, linked to e.g. permitting practices in the Scheldt Estuary must evolve from merely reactive to more proactive. It should thus fully reflect both the ecological interdependence of this transboundary ecosystem as well as the (rising) legal obligations in the context of, amongst other things, nature restoration. Without more systematic use of Espoo procedures and more adaptive, cross-border public participation, environmental governance will remain fragmented, vulnerable to litigation, and unable to meet EU and international legal standards. To facilitate future restoration project, the focus should shift from reactive and ad hoc-participation procedures to more integrated and proactive participation processes, also considering future restoration commitments.

Addressees:

The Flemish Government, the Dutch Government, and possibly the Flemish-Dutch Scheldt Commission (VNSC).

³² Ibid.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Article 1(vii), Espoo Convention.

³⁵ Article 1(viii), Espoo Convention.

Recommendation:

To improve the transparency, legitimacy, and ecological effectiveness of planning and permitting processes in the Scheldt Estuary, Flanders and the Netherlands could develop a joint pilot establishing a 'living consultation' mechanism. This approach should go beyond static, one-off consultation by introducing continuous, adaptive, and inclusive stakeholder engagement throughout the full lifecycle of major projects or restoration plans affecting the estuary. This recommendation responds to recent legal and ecological challenges in the estuary, including litigation related to PFAS contamination, nitrogen deposition, such as the INEOS project, which exposed the shortcomings of current, procedural-only participation. In cross-border areas like the Scheldt Estuary, which is subject to cumulative and evolving environmental stressors, the public input must be able to receive and respond to new information, shifting pressures, and unforeseen impacts.

A 'living' consultation model could include ongoing stakeholder panels (e.g. local communities, NGOs, scientists), regular public dialogue at key decision points, and transparent feedback mechanisms explaining how public input is used. Importantly, this process would also support cross-border engagement, in line with the estuary's transboundary character.

What can be characteristics of a living consultation platform?

- **Continuous:** Not a onetime survey or information collection – but always open for participation
- **Digital-first:** mainly based on the use of apps, dashboards and online platforms. Non-digital options need to be available to avoid exclusion.
- **Inclusive:** Consultation process engages beyond 'traditional' stakeholders, such as citizens, youth or local groups.
- **Responsive:** The process establishes transparent feedback loop so the participants can see if and how input has affected outcomes.
- **Data-integrated:** Can combine the input of the participants with other data (e.g. environmental sensors, public datasets) to provide a more complete and evidence-based foundation.
- **Science-informed:** Consultation is guided by scientific knowledge: topics, scenarios, and options are based on evidence and research; citizen input is evaluated alongside data and models; and discussions are framed within legal and policy boundaries. This ensures participation is realistic, actionable, and policy-relevant.
- **Co-creative:** It allows citizens to actively participate in shaping ideas and co-design policies (meaning it can go beyond the proposal stage)

This mechanism can build upon existing participation obligations, such as Article 6(4) of the Aarhus Convention, Article 6 of the EIA Directive and Article 2(6) of the Espoo Convention, which require effective, early, and inclusive public participation, particularly where transboundary impacts are likely. It also supports the Nature Restoration Law, which emphasises public and stakeholder involvement in restoration planning through the national restoration plans (Article 14(20) NRL)³⁶. From an operational perspective, Flanders and the Netherlands could embed this pilot into an upcoming restoration initiative under the NRL, or within the VNSC governance framework.

³⁶ See also recital 65 to the NRL, stating the importance of giving the public 'early and effective opportunities to participate in the preparation of the [national restoration] plans'.

Added value:

Implementing a ‘living consultation’ mechanism ensures (better) compliance with international obligations on public participation, as set out under the Aarhus Convention, the Espoo Convention, and EIA and SEA Directives. It directly responds to legal and governance shortcomings identified in recent litigation, where current participation practices have proven too ‘static’ and ‘reactive’ to adequately address cumulative and transboundary environmental stressors. The presented participation approach further supports the operationalisation of the Nature Restoration Law’s requirement for inclusive and effective participation (Art. 14(20) in developing national restoration plans, particularly in transboundary areas like the Scheldt Estuary (Art. 14(17)). By shifting from minimal procedural compliance to meaningful, continuous and adaptive participation, it strengthens democratic legitimacy, builds public trust, reduces litigation risks, and enhances the overall quality and acceptability of environmental decisions.

PART III: Funding

Policy Recommendation 4

Improve funding access for citizens’ participation in environmental decision-making

Summary:

Citizen and NGO initiatives play a crucial role in protecting biodiversity (and public health) in the Scheldt estuary, but often face barriers due to limited, unstable, or inaccessible funding. Without adequate financial support, these groups struggle to engage in permitting, legal action, or public consultations—undermining their rights under the Aarhus Convention and broader EU environmental law. Recent court cases, such as those involving PFAS, show the value of civil society in driving accountability, although concerns have been raised that legal actions by NGOs could impact their eligibility for public funding³⁷. To address this, Flanders and the Netherlands could improve access to funding by simplifying procedures, enabling long-term support, and ensuring fair opportunities for smaller grassroots organisations. This would strengthen democratic oversight, ecological protection, and transboundary governance in the Scheldt Estuary.

Context and problem:

(Small), citizen-based initiatives, local initiatives or NGOs are essential in protecting biodiversity and addressing degradation of biodiversity and/or health concerns related to pollution. They can play a vital role in safeguarding environmental quality and biodiversity, also in the context of the Scheldt Estuary. These groups served as early warning actors, community watchdogs, and key contributors to public debates, particularly in complex or politically sensitive contexts such as pollution from PFAS and nitrogen-emissions. However, their capacity to participate meaningfully in environmental decision-making can be limited by unstable or insufficient

³⁷ Example: <https://www.climaxi.be/nieuws/nva-wil-subsidie-climaxi-stopzetten>.

funding and by overly complex administrative requirements for accessing support. This leaves them, for example, unable participate in permitting procedures, respond to development proposals, or initiate legal challenges.

It is important to take note of recent cases where action prompted by legal challenges brought forward by citizens and civil society—such as those related to climate change and PFAS pollution—has led to tangible policy changes. These cases illustrate that pursuing legal avenues is a legitimate and (often perceived) necessary means of addressing environmental and pollution issues. Therefore, the potential for legal action should not be considered a reason to withhold subsidies or limit support for these groups³⁸; rather, it underscores the critical need to empower them to engage fully in environmental governance. Lack of funding or lack of access to funding can undermine effective environmental oversight and delays progress on pressing ecosystem challenges, contrary to the Aarhus Convention's³⁹ guarantees on public participation, access to information, and access to justice in environmental decision-making.

The Aarhus Convention requires Parties 'to endeavour to ensure' that public authorities assist and guide the public in accessing environmental information, participating in decision-making, and seeking access to justice (Art. 3(2)). It also guarantees the right of the public to participate early, effectively, and in a timely manner in decisions on specific activities that may significantly affect the environment (Art. 6). Furthermore, the Convention requires Parties to ensure that members of the public have access to review procedures to challenge environmental decisions or violations of participation rights (Art. 9), and that these procedures are fair, equitable, timely, and 'not prohibitively expensive'. Without adequate financial resources, especially for small citizen-based organisations, these rights cannot be meaningfully exercised, undermining the Convention's purpose and weakening environmental accountability in practice⁴⁰.

Addressees:

Relevant funding authorities in Flanders and the Netherlands, and possibly EU institutions overseeing funding programmes with a responsibility to uphold access to justice and public participation.

Recommendation:

Improve access to public funding for NGOs and citizen-led initiatives working on biodiversity and environmental health, including in the Scheldt Estuary, by:

- Simplify application procedures and reduce administrative requirements to ensure smaller, less-resourced organizations can realistically apply and comply without disproportionate effort.
- Ensure stable, multi-annual funding that enables long-term engagement, independent oversight, and consistent participation in permitting and planning processes—recognising that short-term or project-based funding can jeopardise continuity and effectiveness;
- Create transparent and inclusive funding frameworks that actively facilitate access for grassroots and community-based groups, preventing dominance by larger, more established organizations

³⁸ WP 3 interview.

³⁹ UNECE Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters, Denmark 25 June 1998, available at: <https://unece.org/DAM/env/pp/documents/cep43e.pdf>.

⁴⁰ Interview references from WP3.

This recommendation supports the implementation of public participation rights under the Aarhus Convention, notably the duty to support and recognise environmental organisations (Art. 3(2)) and to ensure meaningful participation and access to justice (Art. 6 and 9). It also complements EU environmental legislation, including the EIA and SEA Directives, which require transparency and public involvement in decisions affecting the environment. Accessible, long-term funding is essential to enable citizen-based actors to fulfil their watchdog, advocacy, and participatory roles, thereby strengthening democratic oversight and biodiversity protection, including in the Scheldt Estuary.

Added value:

Implementing this recommendation could strengthen public participation, transparency, and accountability in transboundary environmental governance. It would empower NGOs and local initiatives to monitor environmental impacts effectively, engage actively in consultations, and, where necessary, legally challenge projects that pose environmental (or health) risks. Such enhanced involvement will support stronger legal compliance, promote better biodiversity conservation, and contribute to the democratic legitimacy of decision-making processes in general and in the Scheldt Estuary context.

This recommendation also links to the application of Article 6 of the Aarhus Convention, which requires public participation in transboundary EIA procedures. Adequate funding is essential to ensure that NGOs and local groups can engage in these processes. Improving access to support enables meaningful participation, helps meet legal obligations, and leads to more inclusive and sustainable decisions in the context of the Scheldt Estuary.

Policy Recommendation 5

Increase funding for large-scale ecosystem restoration

Summary:

Meeting the EU Nature Restoration Law's binding targets requires significant, long-term funding, especially for complex, cross-border ecosystems as the Scheldt estuary. Current funding mechanisms often overlook the administrative, governance, and participatory needs of transboundary restoration. Member States could establish dedicated national funding streams that support both ecological actions and the cross-border coordination, monitoring, and public engagement required under EU and international law. This approach will strengthen legal compliance, improve ecological outcomes, and ensure inclusive, transparent restoration efforts across shared landscapes.

Context and problem:

Large-scale nature restoring is now an explicit legal obligation under the EU Nature Restoration Law. While the Birds and Habitats Directives already contained such restoration obligations, the NRL establishes both a Union-wide ambition and binding national restoration targets. It establishes an EU-wide target of restoring at least 20% of the EU's land and sea by 2030 and all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050 (Art. 1 NRL). In parallel, Member States are subject to binding national targets (Art. 4 and 5 NRL) requiring them to restore at least 30% of the total

area of habitats in poor condition by 2030, prioritising Natura 2000 sites (Art. 4 and 5). This target increases to 60% by 2040 and 90% by 2050.

Achieving these targets will require significant, stable, and long-term funding, particularly for restoration in complex or large-scale ecosystems, including transboundary nature areas, such as the Scheldt Estuary. In setting out the content of the National Restoration Plan, the NRL mentions the estimated financing needs for the implementation of restoration measures⁴¹. Restoring such ecosystems requires not only ecological expertise but also governance mechanisms and financial structures that support cooperation across borders, e.g. harmonization of restoration goals and the integration of legal and administrative systems across jurisdictions and joint monitoring and implementation.

Funding of restoration would cover/include coordination costs, joint ecological assessments, stakeholder engagement across countries, and governance mechanisms that are rarely covered by existing funding tools. More specifically, transboundary restoration must respect international legal obligations on public participation and transparency. The Espoo Convention requires environmental impact assessments and early public consultation where projects may have cross-border environmental effects. The Aarhus Convention guarantees the rights of the public to access environmental information, participate in decision-making, including in transboundary contexts. Ensuring these rights requires not only legal compliance, but also adequate funding to support inclusive participation, communication, and procedural access across borders⁴². National restoration efforts must therefore be supported by a combination of Member State budgets, EU funding and private sectors investments⁴³. Without coordinated and accessible funding mechanisms at the national level, including funding that is specifically adapted to transboundary restoration and its public participation requirements, Member States might risk falling short of their restoration obligations.

Addressees:

This recommendation is primarily addressed to Member State governments responsible for implementing the Nature Restoration Law (NRL) and allocating national budgets for restoration.

Recommendation:

Member States could consider establishing dedicated national funding streams that address/cover the specific needs of transboundary restoration efforts, with particular attention to large, shared ecosystems, such as the Scheldt Estuary. These funding mechanisms could go beyond supporting ecological restoration actions alone. They could also cover the institutional, administrative, and participatory requirements essential for successful cross-border implementation, including coordination between countries, joint monitoring frameworks, and capacity-building across jurisdictions.

Funding should not only support the physical restoration interventions themselves, including the purchase of the necessary terrains and plots of land and financial compensation in light of property rights but also provide ongoing support for the personnel and teams responsible for

⁴¹ Article 15(3)(u) NRL.

⁴² Formulation to depend on EIA obligation.

⁴³ Recital 78 to the NRL states that: 'to ensure meeting the targets and fulfilling the obligations set out in this Regulation, it is of utmost importance that adequate private and public investments are made in restoration. Member States should therefore integrate in their national budgets expenditure for biodiversity objectives, including in relation to opportunity and transition costs resulting from the implementation of the national restoration plans, and reflect how Union funding is used'. See also Article 14 and 15.

maintaining and managing biodiversity as critical ecological infrastructure. This ensures that biodiversity is treated as continuous, resilient infrastructure, rather than only being addressed reactively when problems arise. By funding both restoration works and the people who implement, maintain, and manage them, Member States can secure the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of ecosystem restoration projects.

Importantly, these funding streams should explicitly provide for public participation, transparency, and stakeholder engagement, in line with the obligations under the Aarhus Convention (Art. 6–9 on public access to information, participation in environmental decision-making, and access to justice) and the Espoo Convention (which requires early consultation and public involvement in cases of transboundary environmental impact). National funding frameworks must therefore be structured not only to support technical restoration, but also to enable meaningful inclusion of citizens, NGOs, and local actors across borders. This means that funding should not be limited to physical restoration works but must also support the processes that make restoration legitimate and effective, such as stakeholder dialogue, cross-border consultation, and dispute resolution. By investing in these participatory and governance aspects, Member States can ensure that restoration efforts are both socially supported and legally robust, especially in complex transboundary contexts like the Scheldt Estuary.

Added value:

Developing tailored national funding streams for transboundary restoration will directly support compliance with the NRL's binding ecosystem restoration targets (Art. 4 and 5), as well as the requirement to address financing in the National Restoration Plan (Art. 15(3)). Restoration in the Scheldt estuary (and other nature areas) would moreover contribute to the objectives of the Habitats Directive and the WFD, particularly regarding achieving 'favourable conservation status' and 'good ecological status' respectively.

Additionally, by integrating financial support for cross-border governance, public engagement, and legal transparency, Member States will help ensure compliance with their obligations under the Aarhus and Espoo Conventions. This not only reinforces inclusive environmental decision-making but also strengthens public trust and legitimacy in the restoration process. Finally, accessible and stable funding will enable more effective use of local knowledge and civil society capacity, resulting in more resilient, inclusive, and durable restoration outcomes across the EU.

PART IV: Integration

Policy Recommendation 6

Better integrate biodiversity protection and climate resilience and adaptation

Summary:

Despite legal obligations and clear synergies, biodiversity restoration and climate adaptation remain poorly integrated in the Scheldt Estuary due to fragmented governance, declining restoration drivers, and limited public support. The ongoing 2030 revision (*herijking*) of the Long-Term Vision for the Scheldt Estuary offers a strategic opportunity to embed biodiversity

restoration and climate adaptation as cross-cutting priorities within the existing pillars of the 2005 Scheldt Treaty (accessibility, safety, nature). While the pillars themselves cannot be changed, integrating these themes into their implementation would improve coherence across sectors, increase the legitimacy of restoration projects, and support long-term resilience. Explicitly framing biodiversity as critical natural infrastructure for the future of the Scheldt Estuary — essential for flood protection, climate resilience, water quality and ecosystem services — strengthens its position alongside accessibility and safety in strategic decision-making. Formally recognising biodiversity and climate adaptation as shared priorities helps ensure they are not overshadowed by other interests in decision-making. It supports alignment with EU law and enables more effective, integrated action across sectors and borders.

Context and problem:

Despite growing recognition of the synergies between climate adaptation and biodiversity protection, current governance and implementation frameworks in the Scheldt Estuary fall short of effectively integrating and implementing these agendas. Historically, large-scale ecosystem restoration in the estuary was often driven by compensatory obligations linked to port expansion projects. As the port of Antwerp increasingly focuses on internal optimisation rather than spatial expansion, this external driver for nature restoration has weakened. The resulting vacuum, combined with persistent sectoral compartmentalisation, has made it increasingly difficult to implement restoration measures.

Restoration and climate adaptation are not only policy ambitions but also (emerging) legal obligations. Ecosystem restoration is a requirement under EU instruments, such as the Nature Restoration Law (NRL). Under the EU Climate Law (Article 5), Member States must promote nature-based solutions (NbS) and ecosystem-based adaptation, particularly in vulnerable sectors such as water and agriculture⁴⁴. Also, the WFD imposes legally binding obligations to prevent deterioration and to restore surface waters and groundwater to good status. Moreover, recent jurisprudence — notably the *KlimaSeniorinnen v. Switzerland* ruling by the European Court of Human Rights — confirms that states have positive obligations to implement both mitigation and adaptation measures to protect life, health, and well-being from the serious impacts of climate change⁴⁵. These obligations are further reinforced by the International Court of Justice's Advisory Opinion on the Obligations of States in respect of Climate Change, issued on 23 July 2025, which affirms that states have binding obligations under international law to protect the climate system for present and future generations. Effective implementation of nature-based solutions as climate adaptation measures is supported by the principle that adaptation measures be put in place and effectively applied in accordance with the best available evidence⁴⁶.

However, the implementation of NbS remains limited in Flanders and the Netherlands, often due to governance fragmentation, lack of coordination between sectors, and a failure to make the multifunctional benefits of ecosystem restoration visible to stakeholders (integrating the

⁴⁴ Art. 5(4) of Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 states that: “Member States shall adopt and implement national adaptation strategies and plans, taking into consideration the Union strategy on adaptation to climate change referred to in paragraph 2 of this Article and based on robust climate change and vulnerability analyses, progress assessments and indicators, and guided by the best available and most recent scientific evidence. In their national adaptation strategies, Member States shall take into account the particular vulnerability of the relevant sectors, inter alia, agriculture, and of water and food systems, as well as food security, and promote nature-based solutions and ecosystem-based adaptation”. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32021R1119>.

⁴⁵ Case of *verein klimasenioren Schweiz and others v. Switzerland*, available at: <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22appno%22%3A%2253600/20%22%2C%22itemid%22%3A%22001-233206%22%7D>.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, para. 552.

biodiversity and climate adaptation impacts). Conflicts over land use—particularly between ecological restoration and agriculture—further constrain progress. In the Scheldt Estuary, where population density and economic activity are high, the spatial requirements of NbS (e.g. room for river, wetland reconnection) clash with land-use patterns and economic interests. And while major restoration projects, aimed at flood protection, have been carried out in the Scheldt Estuary during the past decades, it remains uncertain whether this drive can be continued during the next decades.

The VNSC is currently working on the revision or update of the long-term vision (2030), considering new developments and challenges, such as climate change, the energy transition, the shift toward a circular economy, and adjustments in water, environmental, and nature policies. The three pillars (of the 2005 bilateral treaty)—accessibility, nature, and flood safety—are considered in an integrated way to achieve a climate-resilient and sustainable development of the Scheldt estuary⁴⁷. In addition, the Scheldt Council remains to provide a platform for stakeholder dialogue. However, these institutional structures have yet to translate strategic visions into actionable, cross-sectoral implementation pathways. The link between ecosystem restoration and climate adaptation remains unclear to citizens and stakeholders, contributing to polarisation, scepticism (e.g. claims of "fake nature"), and limited social legitimacy for new restoration projects.

Addressees:

Local and regional governments; National environmental and climate ministries; Civil society and citizens networks; and Scientific community

Recommendation:

Integrate biodiversity- climate adaptation link as a cross-cutting theme in the 2030 revision (*herijking*) of the VNSC long-term vision. Although the three pillars of the 2030 Long-Term Vision (accessibility, safety, and nature) are formally established in the 2005 Scheldt Treaty and cannot be changed, the ongoing revision process (*herijking*) offers a valuable opportunity to explicitly embed biodiversity and climate adaptation as a cross-cutting and connecting theme within these existing pillars. Moreover, the framing of biodiversity as critical natural infrastructure for the future of the Scheldt Estuary underscores its essential role in flood protection, climate resilience, water quality, and the provision of ecosystem services. By explicitly integrating biodiversity and climate adaptation as key priorities in the implementation and further elaboration of the three pillars, the 'herijking' can contribute to a more coherent, effective, and future-proof approach for the Scheldt Estuary. This thematic integration strengthens the coherence between nature restoration and climate measures, enhances social legitimacy of projects, and supports the achievement of joint objectives without requiring amendments to the treaty itself.

This approach encourages collaboration between sectors and cross-border actors, ensuring that ecological and climate goals are better reflected in policy decisions, spatial planning, and investments across the Scheldt region, while highlighting biodiversity restoration as a strategic, legally anchored, and societally valuable form of infrastructure for the estuary's long-term resilience.

Added value:

⁴⁷ Langetermijn perspectief voor de natuur van het Schelde estuarium, p. 6., available at: https://www.zeeland.nl/sites/default/files/digitaalarchief/IB24_431c18ba.pdf.

By formally recognising biodiversity restoration and climate adaptation as cross-cutting themes in the 2030 revision, these priorities are less likely to be overshadowed by other interests in decision-making. This approach ensures they are treated as integral components of all three pillars — not as optional trade-offs or secondary considerations. Moreover, framing biodiversity as critical natural infrastructure for the future of the Scheldt Estuary highlights its functional role in flood protection, climate resilience, water quality and long-term socio-economic stability, placing it on equal footing with accessibility and safety. It also reflects their status as binding legal obligations under EU law (e.g. the NRL and EU Climate Law), and supports more coherent, integrated action across sectors and borders. Ultimately, this strengthens both the ecological effectiveness and the legitimacy of future measures in the Scheldt Estuary.

Policy Recommendation 7

Strengthen the system-based governance for the Scheldt Estuary

Summary:

Governance of the Scheldt Estuary remains fragmented along administrative and sectoral lines, despite the estuary functioning as a single, highly interconnected socio-ecological system. Building on the system approach developed in the work of Professor Meire, this recommendation proposes to strengthen the integration of a system-based perspective into transboundary governance structures and decision-making processes. Rather than managing separate components such as water quality, biodiversity, navigation, or flood protection in isolation, the system approach recognises the strong interdependencies between hydrodynamics, sediment dynamics, ecological processes, and human interventions. By translating this perspective into governance, Dutch and Flemish authorities can support more coherent consideration of system interactions and cross-sectoral dependencies, while potentially contributing to improved coordination across policy domains. This is particularly relevant for the coherent implementation of EU environmental law and the long-term resilience of the estuarine ecosystem.

Context and problem:

The Scheldt Estuary is widely recognised in scientific literature as a single, dynamic system in which physical, chemical, ecological, and socio-economic processes are closely interlinked⁴⁸. Early system analyses, notably those developed by Professor Meire and colleagues, demonstrated that interventions in one part of the estuary inevitably generate effects throughout the system as a whole. Activities such as dredging, pollution discharges, or habitat modification influence hydrodynamics, sediment transport, and ecological functioning across the Dutch–Flemish border⁴⁹.

⁴⁸ Meire, P. et al, Het Schelde-estuarium: ecologische beschrijving en een visie op de toekomst (Instituut voor Natuurbehoud 1992), available at: https://purews.inbo.be/ws/portalfiles/portal/18129077/Meire_etal_1992_ScheldeEstuariumEcolBeschrijving.pdf.

⁴⁹ Van Damme, S., Ysebaert, T., Meire, P. & Van den Bergh, E., 1999. Habitatstructuren, waterkwaliteit, en leefgemeenschappen in het Schelde-estuarium. Rapport Instituut voor Natuurbehoud 99/24, Brussel.

Fig. 1.1: Schematische weergave van de verschillende componenten van het Schelde-estuarium (Meire et al., 1997)

Figure above: Schematic representation of the components and processes of the Scheldt estuary and their interactions (Van Damme 1997)⁵⁰.

This system understanding is also reflected in integrated monitoring approaches, which aim to capture interactions between ecological components of the estuary through a coordinated monitoring framework⁵¹. Despite this scientific understanding of the estuary as an integrated system, governance arrangements remain largely organised along administrative and sectoral boundaries. Decision-making responsibilities are divided between Flanders and the Netherlands, while policies for navigation, flood protection, biodiversity conservation, and water quality are often developed and implemented separately. This creates a persistent tension between the ecological functioning of the estuary as a single interconnected system and fragmented institutional governance across administrative levels⁵². As a result, policy coordination across sectors and borders is challenging, particularly when addressing cumulative and cross-border impacts. Without explicitly integrating a system-based perspective into governance, existing policy frameworks—including Natura 2000, the Water Framework Directive, and the EU Nature Restoration Regulation—risk being implemented in a fragmented

⁵⁰ Van Damme, S., Ysebaert, T., Meire, P. & Van den Bergh, E., 1999. Habitatstructuren, waterkwaliteit, en leefgemeenschappen in het Schelde-estuarium. Rapport Instituut voor Natuurbehoud 99/24, Brussel.

⁵¹ Meire P and Maris T, MONEOS: geïntegreerde monitoring van het Schelde-estuarium (Instituut voor Natuur- en Bosonderzoek 2008, available at: https://www.tide-toolbox.eu/pdf/reports/MONEOS_Integrated_Monitoring_of_the_Scheldt_estuary.pdf.

⁵² Meire, P. et al, Het Schelde-estuarium: ecologische beschrijving en een visie op de toekomst (Instituut voor Natuurbehoud 1992), available at: https://purews.inbo.be/ws/portalfiles/portal/18129077/Meire_etal_1992_ScheldeEstuariumEcolBeschrijving.pdf.

See also: Suykens, C. (2018). The law of the river: Transboundary river basin management and multi-level approaches to water quantity management (1st ed.). Antwerpen, Belgium: Intersentia.

manner. This undermines their effectiveness in achieving ecosystem-level objectives in the Scheldt Estuary⁵³.

Addressees:

The primary addressees of this recommendation are the Dutch and Flemish environmental and water management authorities responsible for the implementation of EU environmental legislation and estuarine management. A central role is envisaged for the Vlaams-Nederlandse Scheldec commissie (VNSC) as the main platform for transboundary cooperation in the Scheldt Estuary. Additional addressees include regional planning authorities and agencies responsible for navigation, flood risk management, and spatial planning, whose decisions significantly affect the functioning of the estuarine system.

Recommendation:

To address the identified tension between the ecological functioning of the estuary as an interconnected ecosystem and fragmented governance structures, Dutch and Flemish authorities should strengthen the integration of a system-based perspective in governance approaches for the Scheldt Estuary. This recommendation builds on system analyses describing the Scheldt estuary as a single, dynamic system characterised by strong interdependencies between hydrodynamic, geomorphological and ecological processes⁵⁴. These studies describe interactions between physical, chemical and biological processes across the estuarine system, showing that changes in one part of the estuarine system may have consequences throughout the system as a whole, due to the close interaction between physical, chemical and biological processes. A system-based perspective in governance would require explicit consideration of system-wide interactions and cross-sectoral interdependencies. In practice, this can be reflected in planning and decision-making processes. Plans, programmes, and projects affecting the estuary can take into account interactions between hydrological, ecological, and socio-economic processes, as reflected in empirical analyses of the Scheldt system⁵⁵. Such interactions have been documented between habitat structures, water quality and biological communities within the estuary⁵⁶.

Existing joint monitoring and modelling initiatives, such as those developed under MONEOS, provide system-wide data and analysis of estuarine processes⁵⁷ and can provide a basis for supporting more integrated understanding of system dynamics. From this perspective, existing policy instruments and governance practices could be applied in a way that better reflects system dynamics, for instance by paying increased attention to cumulative and cross-sectoral effects in planning, coordination and evaluation processes.

⁵³ Backes, C., de Haas, J., Cliquet, A. en S. Parramore (2021), Inventarisatie juridisch kader Natura 2000 Langetermijnperspectief voor de natuur van het Schelde-estuarium, Universiteit Gent, Universiteit Utrecht.

⁵⁴ Meire P, Ysebaert T, Van Damme S, Van den Bergh E, Maris T and Struyf E, (2005), The Scheldt estuary: a description of a changing ecosystem, in 540 *Hydrobiologia*; Meire P, Seys J, Ysebaert T and Coosen J, Het Schelde-estuarium: ecologische beschrijving en een visie op de toekomst (Instituut voor Natuurbehoud 1992), available at: <https://pureportal.inbo.be/nl/publications/het-schelde-estuarium-ecologische-beschrijving-en-een-visie-op-de/>.

⁵⁵ Van Damme S, Struyf E, Maris T and Meire P, Habitatstructuren, waterkwaliteit en leefgemeenschappen in het Schelde-estuarium (Instituut voor Natuurbehoud 1999).

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ Meire P and Maris T, MONEOS: geïntegreerde monitoring van het Schelde-estuarium (Instituut voor Natuur- en Bosonderzoek 2008), available at: https://www.tide-toolbox.eu/pdf/reports/MONEOS_Integrated_Monitoring_of_the_Scheldt_estuary.pdf.

Finally, the system approach should be reflected within the governance structures of the VNSC. This could involve integrating system-based principles into strategic documents and strengthening coordination between different thematic policy domains. This would align governance practices more closely with the system characteristics described in the scientific literature.

Operationalisation of system-based governance

- **Biodiversity as a critical infrastructure**

Biodiversity in the Scheldt Estuary should be understood not only as a conservation objective, but as critical natural infrastructure that underpins flood protection, climate resilience, water quality, and ecosystem services. This implies a shift from project-based restoration towards long-term maintenance and enhancement of ecological systems, similar to conventional infrastructure management. By embedding this perspective in investment and planning strategies, biodiversity can function as a structural and adaptive component of the estuarine system, rather than an ancillary policy goal.

- **Integration into spatial planning and infrastructure projects**

Large-scale infrastructure interventions in the Scheldt Estuary, such as dike reinforcements, navigation works, and flood protection schemes, provide key opportunities for integrating biodiversity objectives. Rather than treating ecological measures as separate mitigation, they should be embedded from the earliest planning stages of infrastructure development. This allows ecological restoration, safety requirements, and spatial functions to be addressed in a coordinated and mutually reinforcing way, particularly in areas where land-use pressures are high and multifunctional space is limited.

- **Integrated governance within the VNSC (pillar-based integration)**

The operationalisation of a system-based approach within the VNSC should strengthen the integration of system considerations within the three established pillars of the 2005 Scheldt Treaty: accessibility, safety, and nature. Within this framework, system thinking can be applied by ensuring that decisions taken under each pillar explicitly take account of their interactions with the other pillars. For example, measures related to navigation or accessibility should be assessed in terms of their implications for ecological functioning and flood safety, while nature restoration measures should be considered in relation to navigational constraints and hydraulic dynamics.

This implies a shift from pillar-specific optimisation towards a more coordinated interpretation of pillar objectives, in which trade-offs and synergies between accessibility, safety, and nature are made explicit in planning and evaluation processes. Existing VNSC cooperation structures can support this approach by facilitating structured exchange between thematic domains and by strengthening the consideration of system-wide and cross-border effects within each pillar's decision-making processes.

Added value:

Embedding a system-based governance approach can provide added value for the management of the Scheldt Estuary. By more closely aligning decision-making with the ecological functioning of the estuary, it may contribute to more coherent consideration of interactions between system components, as described in scientific analyses of the Scheldt system. Such an approach may also support a more integrated consideration of cumulative and cross-border pressures, which are inherent to estuarine systems and reflected in the documented interdependencies between ecological components.

In addition, strengthening a system-based perspective may contribute to improved coherence between policy domains and across administrative levels, given the cross-scale interactions observed in the estuarine system. This may be particularly relevant in the context of implementing EU environmental legislation, such as Natura 2000 and the Water Framework Directive, where ecological objectives relate to system-level functioning of water bodies and habitats. Overall, a system-based perspective aligns governance more closely with the ecological reality of the estuary as a single interconnected system, as described in the scientific literature.

Summary and outlook

The Scheldt is an internationally important river and estuary that not only hosts rich biodiversity, but also plays a crucial role in safety, water management and the economy in both Flanders and the Netherlands. The estuary has a long tradition of cooperation and knowledge exchange between governments, scientists, citizens and civil society organisations, resulting in a substantial body of shared knowledge and understanding. At the same time, the current ecological and social situation of the Scheldt presents clear opportunities to better align restoration, climate adaptation and public participation. By making use of these opportunities, the cumulative effects of environmental and climate pressures can be more effectively integrated into decision-making and management. This moment offers an opportunity to build on existing structures and expertise, while at the same time making better use of existing procedures for transboundary cooperation and public participation, as established under the Aarhus and Espoo Conventions. At the same time, alignment with new legal frameworks, such as the EU Nature Restoration Law with its phased obligations, provides strategic guidance for making the ecosystem resilient and multifunctional in the long term. Against this background, the TRANSNATURE project underlines the importance of a more system-based governance approach, in which the Scheldt estuary is explicitly considered as one coherent social-ecological system. This approach provides an overarching analytical and policy framework within which coordination, participation and financing can be better aligned.

Within the TRANSNATURE project, these opportunities and challenges were examined through the categories of “coordination, participation and financing”, which served as a framework for all four case studies. For the Scheldt Case, the category of integration has been added. This analysis, based on stakeholder interviews, literature and case law, indicates that there are clear opportunities and points of attention for further strengthening the functioning of the Scheldt estuary:

- Governance fragmentation: Although the estuary benefits from decades of cooperation between Flanders and the Netherlands and a solid, accumulated knowledge base, policies and

projects are often still organised along sectoral lines. At the same time, existing governance and implementation frameworks are in practice sometimes still strongly structured according to policy domains and/or sectors. This can make it more challenging to design biodiversity restoration, climate adaptation, water management and infrastructure measures simultaneously and in an integrated manner. Particularly where measures affect multiple policy domains, this sectoral organisation may slow progress or limit the use of potential synergies, without detracting from the existing cooperation structures.

- **Limited and static participation:** Citizens, local initiatives and NGOs play an essential role as watchdogs and sources of knowledge, and their involvement has, for example, contributed to identifying PFAS and nitrogen-related problems. Their participation, however, is often formal and one-off, making it difficult to respond in a timely and adaptive manner to cumulative environmental pressures such as nitrogen deposition, PFAS pollution, salinisation and climate change. There is scope to make participation more continuous, inclusive and interactive, so that knowledge, local experiences and concerns can be better integrated into decision-making.
- **Insufficient and uncertain financing:** Both small-scale citizen initiatives and large-scale restoration projects face limited resources and uncertain funding. This hampers continuity, transboundary cooperation and the integration of participation into projects.
- **Risk of legal and societal vulnerability:** Recent court cases show that insufficient attention to cumulative and transnational effects can lead to delays, legal proceedings and a loss of trust. At the same time, these cases demonstrate that well-facilitated participation and cooperation with citizens and NGOs contribute to legitimate, robust and socially supported decisions.

In light of these findings, a system-based governance perspective offers an overarching framework for addressing these challenges in an integrated way by explicitly recognising interactions between ecological processes, policy domains and governance actors. At the same time, the current period offers concrete opportunities. The revision of the Scheldt Long-Term Vision 2030, the implementation of the Nature Restoration Regulation and ongoing infrastructure projects provide an opportunity to structurally connect restoration, climate adaptation and participation.

Recommended Strategic Actions

- **More continuous and adaptive participation (“living consultation”)**
The analysis points to opportunities for organising public involvement in a less one-off and procedural manner, and in a more continuous, adaptive and inclusive way. A “living consultation” approach – for example through digital platforms, recurring dialogue moments and transparent feedback mechanisms – can contribute to better incorporation of new information and cumulative effects. This is consistent with existing obligations under the Aarhus and Espoo Conventions and can strengthen their application in a transboundary context, without the need to reinvent these frameworks.
- **Strengthening the link between biodiversity and climate adaptation**
There are opportunities to position biodiversity and climate adaptation more explicitly as connecting themes within the existing three pillars of Scheldt policy (accessibility, safety and nature). By approaching biodiversity as critical natural infrastructure – with functions for water

management, climate resilience and ecosystem services – coherence between policy objectives can be enhanced and support for restoration measures can be strengthened.

- Improved access to financing for citizen initiatives

Stakeholders/interested parties emphasise the importance of accessible and stable funding for citizen initiatives and smaller NGOs, enabling them to continue fulfilling their role in participation, monitoring and, where necessary, legal procedures. Simplified procedures and multiannual support can contribute to continuity and effective involvement, and support the practical implementation of participation rights as laid down in the Aarhus Convention.

- Targeted and long-term financing for large-scale restoration

For large, complex ecosystems such as the Scheldt, long-term and stable financing is essential. In addition to ecological restoration measures themselves, resources are also needed for coordination, joint monitoring and transboundary participation. By explicitly creating room for these elements within national and European funding streams, the implementation of restoration ambitions can become legally more robust and administratively more effective.

- Biodiversity as structural infrastructure

Several recommendations highlight that nature restoration benefits from an approach in which biodiversity is not only viewed as a restoration challenge, but also as a structural, ongoing investment comparable to other forms of infrastructure. This perspective supports long-term planning, maintenance and the integration of ecological objectives into infrastructure projects, such as dyke reinforcement and water management measures.

- More integrated stakeholder dialogue

Finally, stakeholders point to the added value of broader, integrated consultation processes in which biodiversity, climate adaptation, water management, energy, shipping and spatial planning are discussed jointly. Such processes can contribute to a shared understanding of challenges, the identification of synergies and the strengthening of the societal legitimacy of decisions.

Outlook

The ongoing revision of the Scheldt Long-Term Vision (2030) and the implementation of the EU Nature Restoration Regulation provide concrete and timely opportunities to further embed these recommendations in policy and practice. In this context, a system-based governance approach can serve as an overarching principle for the further integration of restoration, participation and financing within Scheldt policy. By more strongly connecting restoration, participation and financing, initiatives in the Scheldt estuary can:

- better align with existing and emerging legal obligations (such as the Nature Restoration Law, the EU Climate Law and the Aarhus and Espoo Conventions);
- contribute to greater societal support and trust;
- strengthen the ecological resilience and climate resilience of the estuary;
- and further deepen transboundary cooperation.

By building on what already exists while at the same time responding strategically to new developments, the Scheldt can continue to develop as an example of integrated, future-proof river and estuary management, in which nature, society and the economy are approached in a coherent and interconnected manner.

Samenvatting en vooruitblik

De Schelde is een internationaal belangrijke rivier en estuarium, die niet alleen een rijke biodiversiteit herbergt, maar ook een cruciale rol speelt voor veiligheid, waterbeheer en economie in zowel Vlaanderen als Nederland. Het estuarium kent een lange traditie van samenwerking en kennisuitwisseling tussen overheden, wetenschappers, burgers en maatschappelijke organisaties, en er is daardoor al veel gezamenlijk inzicht en kennis opgebouwd. Tegelijkertijd biedt de actuele ecologische en sociale situatie van de Schelde duidelijke mogelijkheden om herstel, klimaatadaptatie en publieke participatie nog beter op elkaar af te stemmen. Door deze kansen te benutten, kunnen de cumulatieve effecten van milieu- en klimaateffecten beter worden geïntegreerd in besluitvorming en beheer. Dit moment biedt een kans om voort te bouwen op bestaande structuren en expertise, terwijl tegelijkertijd beter gebruik kan worden gemaakt van bestaande procedures voor grensoverschrijdende samenwerking en publieksparticipatie, zoals verankerd in de Aarhus- en Espoo-conventies. Tegelijkertijd biedt aansluiting bij nieuwe wettelijke kaders, zoals de EU Nature Restoration Law met haar gefaseerde verplichtingen, een strategisch houvast om het ecosysteem op lange termijn veerkrachtig en multifunctioneel te maken.

Tegen deze achtergrond onderstreept het TRANSNATURE-project het belang van een meer system-based governance benadering, waarbij het Schelde-estuarium expliciet wordt benaderd als één samenhangend sociaal-ecologisch systeem. Deze benadering vormt een overkoepelend analytisch en beleidsmatig kader waarbinnen coördinatie, participatie en financiering beter op elkaar kunnen worden afgestemd.

Binnen het TRANSNATURE-project zijn deze kansen en knelpunten bekeken in de categorieën "coördinatie, participatie en financiering", die als kader dienden voor alle vier de case studies. Voor de Schelde-casus werd hieraan de categorie "integratie" toegevoegd. Uit deze analyse, gebaseerd op stakeholderinterviews, literatuur en rechtspraak, blijkt dat er duidelijke kansen en aandachtspunten zijn om de werking van het Schelde-estuarium verder te versterken:

- Fragmentatie van governance: Hoewel het estuarium beschikt over decennialange samenwerking tussen Vlaanderen en Nederland en een stevig opgebouwde kennisbasis, zijn beleid en projecten vaak nog sectorgebonden. Tegelijkertijd blijkt dat de bestaande governance- en implementatiekaders in de praktijk soms nog sterk langs beleids- en/of sectorale lijnen zijn georganiseerd. Dit kan het uitdagender maken om biodiversiteitsherstel, klimaatadaptatie, waterbeheer en infrastructuurmaatregelen gelijktijdig en geïntegreerd vorm te geven. Met name waar maatregelen meerdere beleidsdomeinen raken, kan deze sectorale ordening de voortgang vertragen of het benutten van mogelijke synergieën beperken, zonder afbreuk te doen aan de bestaande samenwerkingsstructuren.
- Beperkte en statische participatie: Burgers, lokale initiatieven en NGO's vervullen een essentiële rol als waakhond en kennisbron, en hun betrokkenheid heeft bijvoorbeeld bijgedragen aan het signaleren van PFAS- en stikstofproblemen. Hun deelname is echter vaak formele en eenmalig, waardoor het lastig is om tijdig en adaptief in te spelen op cumulatieve milieudruk zoals stikstofdepositie, PFAS, verzilting en klimaatverandering. Er is ruimte om participatie meer continu, inclusief en interactief te maken, zodat

kennis, lokale ervaringen en zorgen beter kunnen worden geïntegreerd in besluitvorming.

- Onvoldoende en onzekere financiering: Zowel kleinschalige burgerinitiatieven als grootschalige herstelprojecten hebben te maken met beperkte middelen en onzekere financiering. Dit belemmert continuïteit, grensoverschrijdende samenwerking en de integratie van participatie in projecten.
- Risico op juridische en maatschappelijke kwetsbaarheid: Recente rechtszaken tonen dat onvoldoende aandacht voor cumulatieve en transnationale effecten kan leiden tot vertragingen, juridische procedures en verlies van vertrouwen. Tegelijkertijd benadrukken deze casussen dat goed gefaciliteerde participatie en samenwerking met burgers en NGO's bijdragen aan legitieme, robuuste en maatschappelijk gedragen besluiten.

In het licht van deze bevindingen biedt een system-based governance perspectief een overkoepelend kader om deze knelpunten in samenhang te adresseren, door interacties tussen ecologische processen, beleidsdomeinen en governance-actoren expliciet te erkennen.

Tegelijkertijd biedt de huidige periode concrete kansen. De herijking van de Langetermijnvisie Schelde 2030, de implementatie van de Nature Restoration Regulation en lopende infrastructuurprojecten vormen een kans om herstel, klimaatadaptatie en participatie structureel te verbinden.

Aanbevolen strategische acties

- Meer continue en adaptieve participatie ('living consultation')

De analyse wijst op kansen om publieke betrokkenheid minder eenmalig en procedureel te organiseren, en meer doorlopend, adaptief en inclusief. Een 'living consultation'-benadering – bijvoorbeeld via digitale platforms, terugkerende dialoogmomenten en transparante feedback – kan bijdragen aan betere verwerking van nieuwe informatie en cumulatieve effecten. Dit sluit aan bij bestaande verplichtingen onder de Aarhus- en Espoo-conventies en kan hun toepassing in een grensoverschrijdende context versterken, zonder deze kaders opnieuw te moeten uitvinden.

- Versterkte koppeling tussen biodiversiteit en klimaatadaptatie

Er liggen mogelijkheden om biodiversiteit en klimaatadaptatie explicieter te positioneren als verbindende thema's binnen de bestaande drie pijlers van het Scheldebeleid (toegankelijkheid, veiligheid en natuur). Door biodiversiteit te benaderen als kritische natuurlijke infrastructuur – met functies voor waterbeheer, klimaatbestendigheid en ecosysteemdiensten – kan de samenhang tussen beleidsdoelen worden vergroot en kan het draagvlak voor herstelmaatregelen worden versterkt.

- Betere toegang tot financiering voor burgerinitiatieven

Stakeholders/ geïnteresseerde betrokkenen benadrukken het belang van toegankelijke en stabiele financiering voor burgerinitiatieven en kleinere NGO's, zodat zij hun rol in participatie, monitoring en – waar nodig – juridische procedures kunnen blijven vervullen. Vereenvoudigde procedures en meerjarige ondersteuning kunnen bijdragen aan

continuïteit en effectieve betrokkenheid, en ondersteunen de praktische uitvoering van participatierechten zoals vastgelegd in het Aarhus-verdrag.

- Gerichte en langdurige financiering voor grootschalig herstel

Voor grote, complexe ecosystemen zoals de Schelde is langdurige en stabiele financiering essentieel. Naast ecologische herstelmaatregelen zelf vraagt dit ook om middelen voor coördinatie, gezamenlijke monitoring en grensoverschrijdende participatie. Door hier expliciet ruimte voor te maken in nationale en Europese financieringsstromen kan de uitvoering van herstelambities juridisch robuuster en bestuurlijk effectiever worden.

- Biodiversiteit als structurele infrastructuur

In meerdere aanbevelingen komt naar voren dat natuurherstel baat heeft bij een benadering waarin biodiversiteit niet alleen wordt gezien als herstelopgave, maar ook als structurele, doorlopende investering, vergelijkbaar met andere vormen van infrastructuur. Dit perspectief ondersteunt langetermijnplanning, onderhoud en integratie van ecologische doelen in infrastructuurprojecten, zoals dijkversterkingen en waterbeheermaatregelen.

- Meer geïntegreerd stakeholderoverleg

Tot slot wijzen stakeholders op de meerwaarde van bredere, geïntegreerde overlegvormen waarin biodiversiteit, klimaatadaptatie, waterbeheer, energie, scheepvaart en ruimtelijke ordening *gezamenlijk* worden besproken. Dergelijke processen kunnen bijdragen aan een gedeeld begrip van opgaven, het identificeren van synergieën en het versterken van maatschappelijke legitimiteit van besluiten.

Outlook

De lopende herijking van de Langetermijnvisie Schelde (2030) en de implementatie van de EU Nature Restoration Regulation bieden concrete en tijdige aanknopingspunten om deze aanbevelingen verder te verankeren in beleid en praktijk. In dit kader kan een system-based governance benadering fungeren als overkoepelend principe voor verdere integratie van herstel, participatie en financiering in het Schelde-beleid. Door herstel, participatie en financiering sterker met elkaar te verbinden, kunnen initiatieven in het Schelde-estuarium:

- beter aansluiten bij bestaande en nieuwe juridische verplichtingen (zoals de Nature Restoration Law, de EU Klimaatwet en de Aarhus- en Espoo-conventies);
- bijdragen aan groter maatschappelijk draagvlak en vertrouwen;
- de ecologische en klimaatbestendigheid van het estuarium versterken;
- en de grensoverschrijdende samenwerking verder verdiepen.

Door voort te bouwen op wat al bestaat en tegelijk gericht in te spelen op nieuwe ontwikkelingen, kan de Schelde zich verder ontwikkelen als voorbeeld van geïntegreerd, toekomstbestendig rivier- en estuariummanagement, waarin natuur, samenleving en economie in samenhang worden benaderd.

Annex 1. The stages of the Article 6(3) and 6(4) procedure

Source: 2021/C 437/01, Commission Notice, Assessment of plans and projects in relation to Natura 2000 sites – Methodological guidance on the provisions of Article 6(3) and (4) of the Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC⁵⁸

⁵⁸ Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ%3AC%3A2021%3A437%3AFULL>.

Annex 2 Comparison of procedures under appropriate assessment (AA), EIA and SEA

	AA	EIA	SEA
<i>Which types of developments are targeted?</i>	Any plan or project which – either individually or in combination with other plans/projects – is likely to have a significant effect on a Natura 2000 site (excluding plans or projects directly connected to the conservation management of the site).	All projects listed in Annex I. For projects listed in Annex II the need for an EIA shall be determined on a case-by-case basis or through thresholds or criteria set by Member States (taking into account criteria in Annex III).	All plans and programmes, or amendments thereof, which: (a) are subject to preparation and/or adoption by an authority at national, regional and local level; (b) are required by legislative, regulatory or administrative provisions; (c) are prepared for agriculture, forestry, fisheries, energy, industry, transport, waste management, water management, telecommunications, tourism, town and country planning or land use and set the framework for future development consent of projects listed in Annexes I and II to the EIA Directive; or which, in view of the likely effect on sites, have been determined to require an assessment pursuant to Article 6 or 7 of Directive 92/43/EEC.
<i>What impacts need to be assessed relevant to nature?</i>	The assessment should be made in view of the site's conservation objectives (which relate to the species/habitat types significantly present on the site). The impacts should be assessed to determine whether or not they will adversely affect the integrity of the site concerned.	Direct and indirect, secondary, cumulative, transboundary, short, medium and long-term, permanent and temporary, positive and negative significant effects on population and human health; biodiversity, with particular attention to species and habitats protected under Directive 92/43/EEC and Directive 2009/147/EC; land, soil, water, air and climate and landscape; material assets, cultural heritage and the landscape; and the interaction between these factors.	Likely significant effects on the environment, including on issues such as biodiversity, population, human health, fauna, flora, soil, water, air, climatic factors, material assets, cultural heritage including architectural and archaeological heritage, landscape and the interrelationship between the above factors.
<i>Who is responsible for the assessment?</i>	It is the responsibility of the competent authority to ensure that the AA is carried out. In that context the developer may be required to carry out all necessary studies and to provide all necessary information to the competent authority in order to enable it to take a fully informed decision. In so doing the competent authority may also collect relevant information from other sources as appropriate.	The developer supplies the necessary information to be duly taken into account, together with the results of consultations, by the competent authority issuing the development consent.	The SEA Directive leaves Member States with a wide margin of discretion in assigning the responsible authorities for SEA. These could either be the authorities in charge of making a plan/programme, the environmental authorities, who are consulted <i>ex lege</i> on the scope and level of detail of the information that must be included in the environmental report, as well as the draft plan/programme and the accompanying environmental report, or the authorities specifically entrusted with running the SEA procedure.
<i>Are the public/other authorities consulted?</i>	The Habitats Directive does not contain an explicit obligation to obtain the opinion of the general public when authorising plans or projects requiring an appropriate assessment. According to the wording of Article 6(3) this has only to be done if it is 'considered appropriate'. However, the Court has clarified that, on the basis of the requirements of the Aarhus Convention, the public concerned, including recognised environmental NGOs, has the right to participate in the authorisation procedure (C-243/15 paragraph 49). This right involves in particular, 'the right to participate "effectively during the environmental decision-making" by submitting, "in writing or, as appropriate, at a public hearing or inquiry with the applicant, any comments, information, analyses or opinions that it considers relevant to the proposed activity" (C-243/15, paragraph 46).	Compulsory – consultation before adoption of the development proposal. Member States must take the measures necessary to ensure that the authorities likely to be concerned by the project (including environmental, local and regional authorities) are given an opportunity to express their opinion on the request for development consent. The same principles apply for consulting the public concerned. In case of likely significant effects on the environment in another Member State, the relevant authorities and the public in that Member State must be consulted.	Compulsory – consultation before adoption of the plan or programme. Member States must consult the authorities, which by reason of their specific environmental responsibilities are likely to be concerned by the environmental effects of implementing a plan/programme. The public, including the public affected or likely to be affected or having an interest in, the decision-making, including NGOs, should be consulted. The authorities and the public shall be given an early and effective opportunity within appropriate time frames to express their opinion on the draft plan or programme and the accompanying environmental report before the adoption of the plan or programme or its submission to the legislative procedure. In case of likely significant effects on the environment in another Member State, the relevant authorities and the public in that Member State must be consulted.
<i>How binding are the outcomes of the assessment?</i>	Binding The competent authorities may agree to the plan or project only after having ascertained that it will not adversely affect the integrity of the site.	The results of the consultations and the information gathered as part of the EIA 'shall be duly taken into account' in the development consent procedure. The decision to grant development consent shall incorporate at least the reasoned conclusion (i.e. the EIA decision) and any environmental conditions attached to the decision.	The environmental report and the opinions expressed 'shall be taken into account' during the preparation of the plan or programme and before its adoption or submission to the legislative procedure.

Source: 2021 Commission Notice, Section 4.1⁵⁹

⁵⁹ Available at [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52021XC1028\(02\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52021XC1028(02)).